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Review Article

A Review of Ethno Medicinal Studies on Respiratory Disorders Management Among Tribal Communities of Gujarat

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ABSTRACT

Gujarat state counts, fifth in the India's tribal population. Tribal communities are known to preserve a rich heritage of traditional knowledge related to medicinal plants and their therapeutic uses. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), nearly 80% of the global population continues to depend on traditional medicine for primary health care needs. The tribal people of Gujarat have long relied on wild medicinal plants for treating a wide range of ailments, reflecting deep understanding of their local biodiversity. Among these, respiratory disorders such as asthma, cough, bronchitis, cold, and other breathing difficulties are commonly managed with plant-based remedies. This review features various wild medicinal plants traditionally used by different tribal groups in Gujarat for the treatment of respiratory problems. The plants discussed are valued for their efficacy, accessibility, and safety, and are often prepared as decoctions, powders or pastes using leaves, roots, bark or seeds. By documenting this indigenous knowledge, the review aims to emphasize the importance of conserving both medicinal plant resources and the cultural wisdom of tribal communities. Such information not only supports the preservation of traditional health practices but also provides a foundation for scientific research that may lead to the development of new drugs for respiratory diseases.

INTRODUCTION

Traditional medicine is defined as “The knowledge, skills and practices based on the theories, beliefs and experiences that are indigenous to different cultures and are used to

maintain health as well as to prevent, diagnose, improve or treat physical and mental illnesses” (World Health Organization). Over the past 100 years, development of large-scale production of chemically synthesized drugs has transformed in most of healthcare worldwide. Despite the advancements, a significant population of

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developing countries still rely on traditional, tribal/ herbal medicines as their primary health care [Ashish Kumar et al (2022)]. Each tribal community has its own unique culture and traditional methods through which practitioners conserve medicinal knowledge and apply strategic approaches to treat many diseases troubling modern society. This traditional wisdom not only helps in managing various ailments but also provides a strong foundation for the discovery and development of modern therapeutic drugs [2]. In modern medicinal research, tribal knowledge on utilization of plants for treating various ailments has put forward vast scope of new drug discovery. Flora of Gujarat state enlisted 1808 angiosperm taxa belong to 155 families and 827 genera. Out of these list, 915 species have been identified to be used medicinally by people [Shah et al. (2012)]. Ethno-medicine is often described as “healing from within,” as it is closely linked to the cultural traditions and practices of local communities [Pieroni A et al. (2005)]. The health system of tribal communities in India is marked by unique challenges that set it apart from both non-tribal health structures within the country and global healthcare models. Tribal health concerns are influenced by distinct socio-cultural practices, rituals, customs, and linguistic diversity that shape their understanding of illness, healing, and healthcare-seeking behaviour. These cultural dimensions often determine the accessibility, acceptance and effectiveness of medical interventions in tribal regions [Deb Roy A et al. (2023)].

[Chandra Shekhar Purohit et al. (2018)] A survey of 1900 adults in North Gujarat (1000 men, 900 women) showed that chronic bronchitis was more common in men (5.65%, mainly from middle-class backgrounds and agricultural occupations) compared to women (2.23%). [Damor et al. (2023)] In a cohort of 1234 elderly patients (>65

years) from Gujarat (773 men, 461 women), respiratory illnesses were more frequent in men. 394 cases required admission, chiefly due to COPD exacerbations, pneumonia, asthma, and pleural disorders. URTI was the most common outpatient issue, while *Staphylococcus* predominated among pneumonia isolates. Newly detected pulmonary TB was also higher in men. [Kakkad et al. (2023)] A hospital-based study in Ahmedabad (2017–2018) examined respiratory admissions among children under six in relation to short-term PM2.5 exposure. Respiratory illnesses formed 21.2% of total admissions, more common in boys and infants. Wheezing disorders predominated. Seasonal risk from PM2.5 was highest in winter, followed by summer and post-monsoon, and lowest during the monsoon. The estimated burden per 100,000 children ranged from 25 (monsoon) to 45 (winter) cases.

2. Collection of data

Literature data (research and reviews) of *Thymus vulgaris* L. were gathered from electronic databases such as PubMed, WoS, Google Scholar, Springer Link, Science Direct and Wiley Blackwell. The peer reviewed journals and E books data were collected. Keyword related data included to know the taxonomy and gaps of research study conducted till now.

3. Ethnobotanical distribution

Several medicinal plants were utilized in the tribal areas of Gujarat to treat respiratory disorders like asthma, cough, bronchitis, breathlessness etc. *Convolvulus prostratus* (Shankhvali) has convolamine, kaempferol, scopoletin, β -sitosterol & ceryl alcohol as bioactive phytochemicals. In Junagadh, people are utilizing this plant to treat respiratory problems such as cough, asthma, chest pain & breathing problem. Burned leaf and jaggery inhale daily till it cure [10, 11]. *Zingiber officinale*

(Adrak), from Zingiberaceae leaves and rhizome use herbal formulations. Recorded that Dangs of tribals in Gujarat use adrak to treat cough, throat pain etc [12, 13]. People of Kuchh - *Tinospora cordifolia* & *Asparagus racemosus* used as cure for bronchitis, cough, cold and other respiratory tract problems [14]. *Ficus benghalensis* (Banyan) Satlasana tribal (Mehsana) people use fresh leaves with honey, to treat asthma [15]. Tribals of Panchmahals, *Borassus flabellifer* L. (Areacaceae) in sakala forest, around 200 to 500 ml of toody collects in the morning to cure tuberculosis. *Sowmide fabrifuga* A. Jus. (Meliaceae), decoction of bark use to cure cough and fever [17].

Ocimum sanctum is available in Dangs & Panchmahals tribes inhales the juice or infusions to treat cold and cough [17]. *Acorus calamus* L. decoction or infusion of rhizome reported that many tribes use to cure pulmonary diseases [19]. *Calotropis procera*, reported that Godhra forest and some other areas of tribes use decoction from leaves, latex & flowers to treat asthma, cough and chest pain [20]. *Curcuma longa* L. In tribal communities of Dangs, Tapi, Panchmahals, Satlasana and Godhra (Vyara), various formulations such as leaf extracts, decoctions, poultices, smoke inhalation, and oral preparations are traditionally employed for the management of cough, cold, asthma, bronchitis, and tuberculosis [21].

Table 1; Ethnobotanical Distribution of Respiratory Medicinal Plants

Scientific Name	Local Name	Distribution	Parts Used	Medicinal Uses [10-21]
<i>Convolvulus prostratus</i>	Shankhawali / Shankhpushpi	Junagadh	Leaves	Breathing Problems Asthma Chest Pain Cough
<i>Zingiber officinale</i>	Adrak	Dangs & South Gujarat Regions	Rhizome & Leaves	Asthma Cough Bronchial Complaints
<i>Tinospora cordifolia</i>	Guduchi	Kachchh, Panchmahals Dangs	Stem (mainly) leaves	Bronchitis Cold Cough Asthma Immunomodulatory
<i>Solanum xanthocarpum</i>	kantakari	Panchmahals Tapi	Whole plant Fruits Roots	Chronic cough Bronchitis Asthma
<i>Asparagus racemosus</i>	Shatavari	Kachchh Tapi	Roots	Cough Cold

		Dangs		
<i>Ficus benghalensis</i>	Vad	Satlasana-Mehsana	Fresh Leaves	Asthma
<i>Borassus flabellifer</i> L.	Adulsa	Sakala forest	Fresh toddy (sap)	Tuberculosis
<i>Sowmida fabrifuga</i> A. Jus.	Patala	Satlasana Panchmahals	Stem bark	Asthma Chronic Bronchitis Cough
<i>Acorus calamus</i> L.	Vach	Dang Panchmahals	Rhizome	Cough Bronchitis Sinus Congestion Asthma
<i>Calotropis procera</i>	Aak	Godhra Tapi	Latex Flower Leaves	Asthma Chronic Bronchitis
<i>Curcuma longa</i> L.	Haldi	Panchmahals	Rhizome	Asthma Cough Throat Inflammation Chest Pain
<i>Justicia adhatoda</i>	Vasaka	Panchmahals Dangs	Leaves	Cough Asthma Bronchitis Tuberculosis
<i>Piper longum</i>	Pipari	Panchmahals Dangs	Fruits Roots	Chronic cough Asthma Bronchitis
<i>Eclipta prostrata</i>	Bhangra	Satlasana	Fruits Roots	Chronic Cough Asthma
<i>Ocimum sanctum</i>	Tulsi	Panchmahals Dangs	Leaves	Cough Cold Throat Pain
<i>Adhatoda vasica</i>	Aradusi	Dang Surat Broach Baroda Panchmahals Sabarkantha Banaskantha	Leaves	Cough Cold Asthma
<i>Terminalia bellirica</i>	Baheda	Panchmahals Tapi	Fruit	Cough Asthma Sore Throat Bronchitis

4. CONCLUSION

The traditional practices of Gujarat's tribal communities reveal an extensive use of medicinal plants for treating respiratory ailments such as asthma, bronchitis, cough, cold, and tuberculosis.

Commonly used species include *Tinospora cordifolia*, *Solanum xanthocarpum*, *Asparagus racemosus*, *Ficus benghalensis*, and several others, each prepared in simple forms like juices, decoctions, poultices, or smoke inhalation. These

remedies reflect a strong relationship between local biodiversity and indigenous healthcare knowledge.

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